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Probiotics and COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped virus with a single-stranded positive sense RNA genome. Vaccine efficacy can be limited by mutations in RNA viruses and search for alternative/additional effective therapies must continue.

Probiotics are generally considered safe. There is a good scientific evidence to support the ability of probiotics to boost human immunity. It is rationale to support the use of probiotics in prevention and treatment of viral infections, including COVID-19. In addition to that, the use of probiotics in COVID-19 can serve as protective factor against cytokine storm and consequential autoimmunity.

INTRODUCTION

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped virus with a single-stranded positive sense RNA genome¹. Vaccine efficacy can be limited by mutations in RNA viruses, as observed for the influenza virus as a representative pathogenic virus^{2, 3}.

The gastrointestinal microbiota has the ability to interact with human cells,

including specific immune cells. These interactions produce different health benefits in the host including regulating gastrointestinal motility; activating and destroying toxins, genotoxins, and mutagens; transforming bile acid and steroids; producing vitamins; absorbing minerals; metabolizing xenobiotic substances; influencing intestinal permeability and barrier functions; and modulating mucosal and systemic immunity; as well as beneficial effects on the skin and upper respiratory tract^{4, 5}.

PROBIOTICS AND COVID-19

Probiotics consist of single or mixed cultures of live microorganisms that can beneficially affect the host by maintaining the intestinal or lung microbiota that play a major role in human health. At present, good scientific evidence exists to support the ability of probiotics to boost human immunity, thereby preventing colonization by pathogens and reducing the incidence and severity of infections. Data from clinical studies of the use of probiotic supplementation to prevent or treat respiratory tract infections (reviewed by

Olaimat and coworkers) show promising benefits of probiotics in reducing the risk of COVID-19. Authors concluded that it is evident that probiotics can reduce the incidence and severity of diseases, suggesting their promise for treating or preventing COVID-19. Probiotics could help prevent COVID-19 by maintaining the human gastrointestinal or lung microbiota because dysbiosis plays a major role in the susceptibility of people to infectious diseases⁶.

Ceccarelli and coworkers concluded in their article that bacteriotherapy (probiotics) could represent a complementary resource for the prevention and restoration of SARS-CoV-2 intestinal mucosa damage through the modulation of gut microbiota and decreasing related inflammation. In other infections, such as HIV, in which intestinal inflammation and related microbiota impairment can affect gut epithelial barrier function, bacteriotherapy (through microbiota surface compounds and metabolites) has been shown to inhibit apoptosis, regulate signalling pathways to produce cytokines, maintain intestinal epithelial homeostasis, and allow recovery of gut mucosal health, thereby attenuating inflammation⁷⁻⁹.

Gohil and coworkers¹⁰ explained in their article that:

1. Probiotic bacteria are generally recognized as safe.
2. Upon administration, probiotics benefit the host by ameliorating the gut health and immune system functioning.
3. The probiotic strains and their metabolites such as bacteriocins have been studied as potential anti-viral agents.
4. Knowing the fact of the high mutational rate of RNA viruses and a major challenge of restricted antibiotic efficacy, the administration of probiotics will help in boosting the host-immunity, and similar to other anti-viral studies it might reduce the symptoms of COVID-19.

Bottari and coworkers explained in their article that the possible benefits of probiotic administration in the framework of COVID-19 infection may be due to their effects on innate and adaptive immunity. Probiotic actions such as influence on cytokines production by intestinal epithelial cells, IgA secretion stimulation to improve mucosal immunity, activation of phagocytosis and macrophage production, modulation of levels and function of regulatory cells, and induction

of dendritic cells maturation, likely affect systemic inflammation. Increasing evidence supports a link between the gut and lungs, thus, further studies should be addressed to investigate a potential role of probiotic in attenuating COVID-19 either through immunomodulatory actions on systemic inflammation or by direct interaction with the lungs. However, not all probiotics are likely to be the same, thus requiring a more targeted approach through the characterization of specific properties of probiotic bacteria at strain level during the development of potential application in COVID-19 and its comorbidities¹¹.

Also, several randomized controlled trials have now shown that microbial modification by probiotics may improve gastrointestinal symptoms and multiorgan inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis, ulcerative colitis, and multiple sclerosis¹², therefore implying that probiotics can be a protective factor in autoimmune conditions.

COVID-19 can cause cytokine storm and even trigger autoimmunity in susceptible patients, hence the use of probiotics in prevention and treatment of COVID-19 can serve as protective factor against cytokine storm and consequential autoimmunity.

CONCLUSION

SARS-CoV-2 is an enveloped virus with a single-stranded positive sense RNA genome. Vaccine efficacy can be limited by mutations in RNA viruses and search for alternative/additional effective therapies must continue.

Probiotics are generally considered safe. There is a good scientific evidence to support the ability of probiotics to boost human immunity. Therefore, it is rationale to support the use of probiotics in prevention and treatment of viral infections, including COVID-19.

In addition to that, several clinical studies confirmed that microbial modification by probiotics may improve gastrointestinal symptoms and multiorgan inflammation in autoimmune diseases hence the use of probiotics in COVID-19 can serve as protective factor against cytokine storm and consequential autoimmunity.

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